

4. The history of the discovery and exploration and exploitation of Africa and 'Atomica' by the "white-man", are in effect identical colonial processes.

In other words, nuclear reactors are the modern equivalent of the African Slave Trade. History is repeating itself.

The history of Europe's involvement with Africa began with Portuguese sailors venturing south from their home ports, and mapping the coastline of the African continent. Then the other sea-faring nations of Europe, the British and the Dutch, followed suit and in due course established settlements in South Africa and trading posts (with a fort or two) where the continental rivers discharged into the sea.

Even before the Europeans arrived in Africa, a slave trade was operating at a local level. But now, with the British jumbo boats capable of transporting several hundred men and women in one vessel, there was the capacity to ship ten million or more African people across the Atlantic Ocean to work as slaves in the sugar cane plantations and cotton fields and mills being developed in the Americas and the Caribbean.

An inquiry by British physicists into the nature of the atom could not help but use the same resources and mindset that had successfully mapped and then colonised much of Africa. My reading of the situation is that because the focus of the physicists was on determining the physical properties of the particles in the atom, then no one saw or thought of the atomic particles as an whole, as being the indigenous native population who occupy the sub-continent of "Atomica".

The realisation of the copious quantities of energy locked up in the atoms led to the development of the atomic bomb. Then nuclear reactors were designed and built to use the same fission process to control the extraction of heat from the atoms.

A comparison of the fission process going on in a nuclear reactor with the capture and transportation of African tribal people to a distant lands, where their physical energy is harnessed to power the new industries being developed in the Americas ... is a slow to realise but virtually identical story.

There is virtually no difference in universal terms between the African Slave Trade and what goes on inside each and every nuclear reactors, except here the devastation of the atoms, the family systems of the particle population, goes on out of sight, in an whole other dimension. The operators of the reactors, guided by government regulations, take elaborate precautions to insure that no one will hear or feel the distress and sadness of the fissioned particles, the effect we know as radiation. To my mind, the radiation of the fissioned particles is synonymous with 'the Blues' of the African people obliged to work as slaves burnt-out and likely to remain blue for the next twenty thousand years or so.

The colonisation of Africa has come to an end but now the very same parties are busy with the colonisation of 'Atomica', and sell their electricity to civil society as a technically innovative energy that is beneficial for the climate change issue which now looms over the future. No mention is made by the advocates of nuclear electricity of the scorching pain and searing sadness that lives on in the vast population of fissioned particles.

When my interest in a metaphysical understanding of the nuclear subject reached a certain level, I sought work at **Dounreay, the nuclear reactor here in northern Scotland.**

I obtained work as a geological technician on a drill rig which was employed in an investigation of the geology and hydrology of the rock strata in the vicinity of the nuclear reactors. The investigation was to determine if the site would be suitable for the development of a nuclear waste repository. In the end, the engineers determined that it was not. Nonetheless, I was on site for six months and during this time had several profound realisations that I will outline here:

As I have already indicated, I grew up in a British colonial household and was entirely familiar with the outlook and attitudes of the British Colonial Service, which in turn reflects the imperious nature of Britain as a whole. I don't mean to be too judgmental and disapproving, since these values also found a home in me, more than I care to say. But in this instance, my experience of the orderly, disciplined, remote and cold-hearted view and treatment of the particle population being fissioned in the reactor brought me to see how we British, and indeed all the nuclear nations, are now working in the Atomic World as colonists. History is repeating itself. We British in particular, with our disdain for displays of emotion, think it clever and entirely acceptable to discount and ignore the extraordinary distress and despair of the fissioned particles. Because they become radioactive, they are seen as unclean, as lepers, as somehow guilty, to be avoided and not really our responsibility.

The knowledge that informs these comments comes from my experiences of visiting the site laboratory which was located beneath the reactor hall itself. One of the duties of the laboratory was to routinely examine the fuel rods which hold the pellets of uranium fuel that are being fissioned. The rods are carefully designed with an open lattice-like structure that both contains the pellets and also allows the liquid sodium to circulate through the rods and burning pellets, in order to recover the heat generated by the fission process. When the uranium fuel was spent, the by-now highly radioactive fuel rods were withdrawn from the reactor and conveyed by remote handling through a tunnel to a sealed chamber alongside the main room of the laboratory. Here workmen used glove boxes to reach through the chamber wall and cut up the used fuel rods, readying them for inspection.

In spite of the precautionary design of this process, the laboratory room became saturated with the feelings of radiation that simply penetrated the walls or leaked in through the glove boxes.

I visited the laboratory in the first instance with a guided party of visitors. The tour was led by two Scottish women who were employed, along with others, to staff the Visitors Centre. Our two were friendly and likeable with their bright and chatty nature so I was taken aback with how this changed as we passed through an air-lock in order to enter the laboratory. The two women became very strict and anxious as we entered this long and seemingly dark room, with its many consoles of flickering red and green lights. It was unusually hot in there. The air was heavy. We were all wearing outdoor clothes. No great surprise then when one of our party fainted.

I knew we would have to wait while this person recovered, so I retreated to a corner of the long room and sat on a box listening to the extraordinary sadness I felt welling up in me. I couldn't shake it off or explain it because I had joined the tour in really good heart. Then, after a while, I realised this was not my sadness, this was not my despair. These feelings were already here in this long room, with the glove boxes built into one wall, with windows above them which looked into the parallel chamber where fuel rods, some of them cut into pieces, were laid out in racks.

The Reactor Hall, Dounreay.

The person who fainted was better. The guides rounded us up and took us away from this gloomy place. That was the end of the tour. We handed in our dosimeters and hard hats. Tea and biscuits were served in the Visitors Centre. I sought out one of the guides and told her about the dark sadness I had felt in the lab. She turned away, there were tears in her eyes. She shook her head and wouldn't engage with me.

"This is the place", I remember saying to myself. Like the story of Bluebeard, who lavished his wife with gifts but warned her never ever to visit the chamber beneath his castle, even though he gave her a key to the door. Here was the one place in the whole operating system where there was a taste of the emotional content of radiation. A glimpse of the sentient nature of the particle world. The intense distress and sadness of the fissioned particles could not be contained. The feelings leaked through the walls and glove boxes or their windows. No one stayed there for long. The workmen were stoic, worked quickly and left.

Inside view of the empty Fast Breeder Reactor at Dounreay

I am able to write about this because I became acquainted in the canteen with the young graduate who was in charge of the laboratory. He had addressed us when we first entered the place, explaining its purpose to the tour party. I told him I was curious about the metaphysics of nuclear energy and felt he already had a sense of what I was talking about. In fact, he was sympathetic. It's not really possible to work in that kind of an environment without our imagination thinking outside the box. So he was okay with me then returning on other occasions when again I just sat quietly and felt into the feelings within that hot closed space.

I'll summarise my experience like this: how the effect was like sitting at the edge of an ocean of sombre emotions. From the ocean, a steady series of slow moving waves, waves of an immense sadness, washed over and through me. Slow moving waves of a hot dark sadness coming steadily from that black ocean. I tried conversing with the women in the Visitors Centre on a couple of occasions about my visits. They were appalled that I chose to go back. The laboratory was shrouded with taboo thoughts and feelings. They were spooked that I even sought to talk about my experience of the place. I'm sure they talked about it amongst themselves. But maybe not. I know they feared being on duty and having to go there.

On the other hand, I was quite upbeat and pleased with myself. This was exactly what I had coming looking for, even while I didn't really know what I was looking for. I told the men who managed the reactor, whom I would meet in the canteen, of my experiences. This one man in particular listened to me and said I was wasting their time. They were so busy dealing with the physics of the reactor, he said, they did not have the time to concern themselves with the metaphysics. But I am moved to say that this same man then asked me if I would like to talk with the Chief Physicist about my experience. This surprised me, but I said yes, and he said he would try and arrange it.

So I went one evening in the company van and parked in the winter darkness outside his home on the outskirts of Thurso. I rang the doorbell and his wife let me into the house, showed me to a study. He was a short-statured man, but highly energetic in his demeanour and he was not shy about immediately expressing his anger that someone like me had found his way into his operation. "Who had given me permission to visit the laboratory", he demanded of me straight off.

I told him I had joined a tour which at that time included a visit to the site laboratory. He was fuming. "You anti-nuclear people get in the way of progress", he shouted at me. I, meanwhile, was being a cool cucumber and told him that I wasn't anti-nuclear. In fact (and I emphasized this) I said I might well be the most pro-nuclear person on the whole site.

Our minds barely met. He was bristling with antipathy towards me. I said something along the lines of how useful I thought it was to have some sense of the emotional content of radiation. He could not really register the things I said. "That's not scientific!" was his main response. He said that he would have me fired if I went near the laboratory again. Then his wife brought in a tray of tea things and he turned on her and shouted at her. It was an absurd situation. I excused myself quite politely and left. The wife let me out and apologised for him, the loyal woman.

I thought later how impossible it would be for the tour guides to contribute their experiential knowledge of radiation to this hierarchical system of single-minded masculine authority. Our knowledge of the particle world and its sentience and endless pain is made virtually inaccessible by the institutionalised patriarchy and misogyny that is in the driving seat of an inquiry that I feel was originally the quest of Humanity to know the universal nature of our Universe. To know if there is life elsewhere in our Universe. This physics-only approach can not do it.
